

PREVENTION OF OFFENSES CURRENT ISSUES

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Annotation

This article provides information and recommendations on the role of crime prevention in the fight against and prevention of crime and the importance of public control in this area, as well as foreign experience.

Keywords: crime, crime prevention, types of responsibility, public control, social rehabilitation, antisocial behavior, fight against crime.

The peaceful life of citizens in Uzbekistan and the increase in their trust in law enforcement agencies are directly related to the level of effective organization of work on crime prevention and crime fighting by these agencies. The fight against crime has always been considered a serious and important issue of the state. People want to live in peace and quiet, and for that, peace must be ensured in the country. Where there is peace, there will surely be blessing and development.

Today, in order to maintain and strengthen law and order and ensure the safety of every member of the society, a wide range of preventive measures are being carried out based on the close cooperation of the internal affairs bodies with the relevant ministries and agencies, civil society institutions.

The main responsibility for the prevention of crimes belongs to the internal affairs bodies and the National Guard. they focus The causes and circumstances of the offense are identified and eliminated with the help of quick-search activities.

In each of his speeches, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that the main task of the agencies responsible for the field is not to find and punish the criminal, but to identify the circumstances that created the conditions for the commission of the crime, especially to pay special attention to work with systemic problems. is insisting.

As we all know, crime in the social sense is a behavior capable of endangering the rights and interests of society, citizens and public associations, which makes it difficult for the development of social relations and causes their disruption. As a result of this, various levels of disappointments begin to occur in the society, and the society itself declines.

At this point, if we define the concept of crime prevention in the legal sense, "crime" means an act (action or inaction) that is dangerous for society[1], and

in another source, crime is established in society and the law It is defined as violation of the established order or the rules of social life in general.

In general, an offense is considered a socially dangerous act (action or inaction) and the responsibility for its commission is determined based on the sphere of law: a) civil; b) disciplinary; c) administrative; g) divided into criminal types. In encyclopedic and explanatory dictionaries, the word "prophylaxis" means the Greek word "prophylaxis" - "protector, preventer" [2].

Since the first years of independence, comprehensive measures have been implemented in our republic to prevent crimes and combat crime, and significant positive results have been achieved in the provision of law and order in the country. However, in most cases, there are also cases where crime prevention is considered to be the duty of law enforcement agencies only.

According to the Decree No. 27 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2021, "On approval of the concept of public security of the Republic of Uzbekistan", entities that ensure public security are the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Internal Affairs , the National Guard, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the State Security Service, the General Prosecutor's Office, the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development, the Ministry of Health, local government bodies, as well as other state bodies and organizations , citizens' access to self-governing bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and subjects involved in ensuring public safety is determined.

In fact, in our opinion, the implementation of crime prevention is the activity of cooperation not only of law enforcement agencies, but also of public organizations, citizens' self-government bodies, family and educational institutions, and includes legal, social, takes educational processes. That's why we can't be wrong to say that the view that only law enforcement agencies are responsible for combating violations and crime is not justified nowadays .
DECREE NO. 27 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan " On approval of the concept of public security of the Republic of Uzbekistan" also provides a completely new mechanism for organizing work in the direction of ensuring public security based on the principle of "serving the interests of the people" and procedures have been introduced, and establishment of mutual purposeful cooperation of state bodies with public structures implied. [3]

of the Republic of Uzbekistan In accordance with the Law " On Public Control " , public control is carried out in relation to the subjects of crime prevention, as

well as in relation to the objects of crime prevention. This is directly reflected in the prevention of bullying through the active participation of citizens and public associations. [2] Citizens actively participating in the fight against crime , approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 15 of January 8, 2018 [3] " On the procedure for encouraging citizens and public organizations for their active participation in crime prevention and crime prevention " is encouraged according to the regulations . this situation , we can see that methods and forms of prevention are interrelated. That is, the method of stimulation is used for measures implemented within the framework of prevention [4] .

Currently, a number of law enforcement bodies, including internal affairs bodies, have created a solid legal framework in order to transform them into a social structure that serves the interests of the people, but the lack of legal description in preventive practice, the use of legal norms by the prosecutor's office, justice, internal affairs and judicial bodies in this direction indicates that there is no single approach in the activity [5]

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. In his speech in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis, Mirziyoyev spoke about the prevention and fight against crime , emphasizing that in recent years, a number of works have been carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to prevent and fight against crime, but there are still issues in the field that are waiting for their solution. past Also, in the appeal, 12 thousand people or 25 percent of the more than 47 thousand people who committed crimes in our country last year were young people, and this indicator exceeded 39 percent in Kashkadarya, Khorezm regions and Tashkent city, and more than 38 percent in Andijan and Namangan regions. It was added that mobile meetings of the Senate were held in the mentioned regions, and this issue was not seriously discussed [6] .

In fact, the majority of crimes are committed by people who do not have a fixed job, have a family, are addicted to alcohol, use drugs, or have previous convictions.

In order to prevent the commission of offenses by such persons, their social rehabilitation, i.e. providing legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical and other types of assistance to persons with antisocial behavior, prone to committing offenses, and offenders , as well as ensuring their employment by taking measures aimed at instilling in them the norms and rules of behavior accepted in the society, as well as developing entrepreneurship is of great importance.

When it comes to this, nowadays in our country, special attention is being paid to the development of entrepreneurship and the elimination of the problems faced by them, they are given wide privileges and opportunities, and thus employment of the population. Nevertheless, today in our country more than 12,000 families have problems within the framework of various family-marital relations that can cause violations, of which 4,809 are troubled families.

The above-mentioned indicators require us to strengthen the measures aimed at preventing violations and crimes. The world practice of combating crime shows that no country has been able to achieve the desired results in the fight against crime by only punishing the criminals. Also, in this regard, a number of our legal scholars, in particular, H. Odilkoriev and I. Tultyev, have expressed the following opinions: the goal of completely eliminating crime in the implementation of the fight against crime is not true, the state of crime and the fight against it are necessary. As can be seen from the conditions, it can be carried out sometimes effectively, and sometimes ineffectively. It seems that the complete elimination of crime is a very difficult and impossible dream [8].

It can be seen that it is a more effective way to prevent crime than to fight against it. The world community is concerned about the implementation of an effective crime-fighting policy. In this regard, the problems of protecting the individual, his rights and freedoms, the interests of society and the state, property, natural environment, peace and human security from criminal aggression, as well as establishing a modern and effective system of crime prevention are becoming increasingly global and urgent.

As we mentioned above. In our country, a number of regulatory legal documents aimed at fighting crime and preventing crimes have been adopted. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention" adopted on May 14, 2014, which defines the main tasks of crime prevention. They consist of:

ensuring the protection of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of the individual;

raising legal consciousness and legal culture in the society, strengthening legitimacy, as well as forming an intolerant attitude towards corruption;

to identify, study, and take measures to eliminate the causes of violations and the conditions that make them possible;

social rehabilitation and social adjustment of victims of crime, persons prone to committing crimes, persons who have committed crimes, including previously convicted and released from places of deprivation of liberty;

reduce the risk of individuals becoming victims of crime;

to ensure mutual cooperation and coordination of activities of bodies and institutions that directly implement and participate in crime prevention [6] .

According to S. Khojakulov: "Crime prevention is within the scope of the powers given by the law, maintaining public order, ensuring the safety of citizens, identifying and eliminating the causes of crimes and the conditions that enable them, using the opportunities of sectoral services effectively, the legal awareness of citizens and culture formation, as well as identification of persons with antisocial behavior and offenders, correcting their morals through preventive measures [10] .

fight against crime and the prevention of violations, it is necessary to use all possibilities to prevent these antisocial situations from occurring . We are below We would like to give some suggestions for improving the system of crime prevention and crime prevention :

- Establishing cooperation with relevant organizations to provide employment to the temporarily unemployed population aged 18-30 included in the "Youth register" and to involve them in socially useful activities;

- targeted work with young people who are inclined to commit or have committed offenses and control their involvement in useful activities;

- in cooperation with short-term vocational training centers, young people who are prone to committing crimes or who are on the probation service list are involved in regular work activities by training them in a certain specialty on a quarterly basis and providing them with work. to do;

to help our citizens who want to work abroad by organizing short-term language and vocational training courses and training in a certain specialty ;

- further improvement of work in this regard by providing legal explanations to young people who have committed offenses in the institutions and neighborhoods where they are studying, in the presence of their close relatives, to what extent their actions will harm them and the surrounding citizens;

We think that the above suggestions will definitely work. The systematic reforms that are being carried out in our country in terms of crime prevention and combating crime serve only and only to ensure the peace and tranquility of our people, and the only goal of these projects is to ensure the peace of the population and thereby contribute to the sustainable development of society . consists of swelling. We are all responsible for this.

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